

Implementation Tacit Knowledge, Internal Knowledge on Performance Management: (Systematic Literature Review)

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ABSTRACT

This paper is to find the results of the implementation of the variables used in this paper which have been used in the research findings, problems and phenomena in this paper as illustrations and solutions from the research findings in the literature. A thorough literature review was conducted as part of the research methodology for this paper. A selection of related scientific articles were collected, analyzed, and reviewed as part of the literature review. The scope of the study was determined based on scores using the PICO framework (population problem, intervention, comparison). The implementation of these three variables already exists, but it is not related to all the variables in one literature in one paper, this paper provides an answer that these variables already exist, and the problems presented above are answered even though they are not optimal and satisfactory in the paper this. The implementation of the three variables in qualitative results is proven and answers problems that are not yet satisfactory.

INTRODUCTION

In large, dynamic organizations, some individuals have knowledge that is not explicitly documented but is invaluable in managing company performance. One individual who has this kind of knowledge is a senior manager who has been dedicated for years to developing the human resources department (Syamsuri et al., 2022). It is important to understand that this knowledge is called tacit knowledge. It is knowledge that is not easily measured or measured but plays a key role in the success of human resource departments and the organization as a whole (Rahayuningtyas et al., 2023). Individuals of these employees have a deep understanding of how various internal and external factors can affect employee performance (Judge & Robbins, 2017). Although all performance metrics are measured routinely, individuals in organizations have the unique ability to read between rows of those numbers. It can identify trends and patterns that may not be visible to others, such as the influence of internal policy changes on employee motivation (Edwards & Edwards, 2019).

Internal knowledge of performance management also includes its ability to build relationships between individuals in organizations (O'Keeffe, 2013). It knows that employee performance is not only influenced by their technical competence, but also by their relationships with superiors, co-workers, and company culture. An integral part of successful performance management in organizations. Being a mentor to many young managers in this organization, sharing his unwritten knowledge of performance management (Zachary & Fain, 2022). He teaches them that this knowledge is not only important for improving employee performance but also for creating a strong and inclusive corporate culture, understanding the importance of using this internal knowledge in forming effective performance management strategies. He knows that not all knowledge can be deciphered in formal documents (Becerra-Fernandez & Sabherwal, 2014). Therefore, he ensures that various team meetings, casual discussions, and other information forums become a means for sharing tacit knowledge among his team members.

Always be ready to adapt performance management strategies according to changes in the business environment or organizational needs. His implicit knowledge allows him to quickly respond to changing situations and find appropriate solutions in real-time (Wong et al., 2019). This represents a significant competitive advantage for organizations because they can cope with market changes faster and more efficiently. The positive influence of tacit knowledge possessed by individual employees is also seen in the high retention rate of employees and their satisfaction at work (Swarnalatha & Prasanna, 2013). Employees feel valued and supported by management because their internal knowledge creates an inclusive work environment and supports their professional development. has an important role to play in helping organizations create a strong learning-based culture (Maamari & Saheb, 2018). He understands that knowledge is not static and that organizations need to constantly adapt and evolve to remain competitive. Therefore, he encourages his team to always look for opportunities to improve performance management

(Collins, 2016). Through regular discussions, training, and evaluation sessions, this employee facilitates shared learning among his team members. They share experiences, knowledge, and insights to continuously improve their performance management practices. This is what keeps the human resources department in the organization relevant and effective in the face of continuous change.

Understand the importance of maintaining the confidentiality and security of internal knowledge. While sharing this knowledge is invaluable, it also recognizes that there is confidential information that should not be disclosed to outside parties or even unauthorized team members (Pearlson et al., 2019). Therefore, ensuring that such knowledge is only shared with individuals who are reliable and adhere to the confidentiality policy of the organization. His important role in the organization, not only leads in terms of performance management but also in facilitating the continuous learning process and maintaining the security of internal knowledge (Dierkes, 2003). These organizations have felt the positive impact of the implicit knowledge possessed in achieving their strategic goals and creating an innovative and adaptive culture. His internalized knowledge has helped the company to continuously grow and improve its performance, and this is what makes it so valuable in the world of performance management (AYDIN, 2018).

Internal knowledge or tacit knowledge is often a key factor in achieving strategic goals. As organizations point out, having individuals who understand the value of knowledge between the lines and can use it to manage employee performance is an invaluable asset (Hislop et al., 2018). That is why a smart organization will always value and facilitate this kind of knowledge sharing because it is one of the foundations of success in the long term. Tacit knowledge or internal knowledge between the lines can help an organization manage employee performance, adapt to change, and create a productive and learning-based work environment (Colquitt et al., 2014). With individuals who understand the value of this knowledge, organizations can continue to thrive and thrive in a dynamic business environment. Problems related to tacit knowledge or internal knowledge in performance management in an organization can include several aspects that can be obstacles to the success and growth of the organization, if the organization relies heavily on internal knowledge that only one or a few individuals have, then it can become a serious problem (Rebelo et al., 2019). If the individual leaves the organization or is no longer available to share his or her knowledge, the organization can experience difficulties in performance management, Tacit knowledge is often difficult to measure and evaluate objectively. This can make it difficult for organizations to assess the effectiveness of performance management and identify areas where improvements are needed, another problem that may arise is the lack of action to extract and disseminate existing internal knowledge. If the knowledge is not shared effectively throughout the organization, then it will become useless.

If employees who have important internal knowledge retire or move to another company, then the organization can face significant knowledge loss. The purpose of this paper is to find the results of the implementation of the

variables used in this paper that have been used in research findings, problems and phenomena in this paper as an overview and solution of the findings of the research results of the literature. A thorough literature review was conducted as part of the research methodology for this paper. A selection of related scholarly articles are collected, analyzed, and reviewed as part of a literature review. The scope of the study was determined based on scores using the PICO framework (population/problem, intervention, comparison). Table 1 presents a literature review of several journals currently available along with a list of study area boundaries. Table 2 is provided below. The following is the description and presentation of article conclusions based on research article metrics.

Tabel 1.
Ringkasa PICO

Komponen	Keterangan
Population/problem	Staff
Intervention	Human Resources
Comparison	n/a
Outcome	Statement of findings

LITERATURE REVIEW

Making research questions, searching the literature, and selecting research are research steps. Data collection, eligibility standards, and quality checks will all be present. In your research paper, include research questions about the importance and dedication of employee retention programs as well as literature searches using the Google Scholar database and other literature sources. The data, or the final step, is. Data mining capabilities to accurately synthesize data and relate it to research findings. The finished matrix table shows how data extraction works.

Figure 1. Scientific Article Selection Process

METHODOLOGY

Tacit Knowledge

Knowledge that cannot be easily expressed or communicated to others orally or in writing is referred to as tacit knowledge. It is deeply embedded in a person's cognitive processes and is often acquired through experience, observation, and practice. Explicit knowledge, which is easy to express and codify, is often contrasted with tacit knowledge. Tacit knowledge includes things like intuition, creativity, and ability that have been honed through repetition and experience (Hibbi et al., 2020). Many industries, such as knowledge management, requirements engineering, and sustainable agriculture, rely on tacit knowledge (Curry & Kirwan, 2014; Wipawayangkool & Teng, 2016). Structured on-the-job training, coaching and job rotation can have a significant impact on employees' ability to acquire new knowledge and apply it to their work. The ability of employees to learn and apply tacit knowledge in their work can also be directly influenced by factors in the work environment, such as support from colleagues and supervisors. Collaborative research, workshops and seminars are the best methods to transfer tacit knowledge among agricultural scientists and improve their efficiency (Nderema et al., 2022). Creating mentoring programs, encouraging employees' free participation in tacit knowledge-sharing efforts, rewarding staff for their contributions to the effort, and fostering teamwork among employees can all assist in tacit knowledge transfer (Kiwelu et al., 2020).

Internal Knowledge

Internal knowledge is an understanding that belongs only to a person or a group of people and is difficult for outsiders to obtain. It includes knowledge embedded at a deep level in human cognitive processes, as well as intuition, creativity, and skills perfected through practice and experience. External knowledge, which can be easily expressed and communicated through written or oral communication, is often contrasted with internal knowledge. Personal beliefs, values, and life experiences are examples of internal knowledge, as are organizational culture and history (Alexander, 2020; Gemünden, 2015). By including it in the decision-making process, internal knowledge can be used as a decision-making tool. Using big data analytics to base decisions on facts, not hunches or buried internal knowledge, is one way to achieve this (Osuszek et al., 2016). Internal knowledge such as personal beliefs, values, and experiences can be taken into account when creating conceptual models to address factors influencing food choice. In the context of tourism fraud, understanding the tourism decision-making process can improve fraud prevention by examining external and internal cues and signals and identifying multiple heuristic strategies (Chen & Antonelli, 2020; Xu et al., 2022).

Performance Management

The term performance management refers to a set of formal and informal mechanisms, processes, systems, and networks that organizations use to communicate the main goals and objectives set by management to support and

facilitate ongoing management and analysis of strategic processes through performance planning, measurement and management, as well as comprehensive performance rewards and management, performance management includes goal setting, employee direction, Metric development, creation of performance data through performance measurement, performance reporting, and use of performance data.(Rajala & Laihonen, 2018). A performance management system is a comprehensive strategy for managing performance that has many different parts and steps. By utilizing these elements, organizations can enhance their capacity for goal achievement, foster organizational learning and change, and maximize the advantages of their offerings (Banda, 2022).

By analyzing, planning, measuring, controlling, and rewarding performance, organizations can support strategic processes and sustainable management. Performance management refers to a collection of formal and informal mechanisms, processes, systems, and networks that organizations use to communicate key goals and objectives set by management. and more broadly for supporting and facilitating organizational learning and change, performance management, and. Setting goals, leading employees, creating metrics, generating performance information through performance measurement, performance reporting, and using performance data are some of the essential elements of a performance management system. In addition, the steps involved in creating a performance management system are discussed, as well as common issues with doing so. In the public sector, where it is used to improve public services, performance management is crucial (Obermayer et al., 2022).

Table 2. Journals, Publishers, and Findings

No	Nama Artikel	Penulis	Jurnal	Penerbit	Temuan
1.	The Evaluation System of Enterprise Tacit Knowledge Management Performance	(Yang, 2014)	International Conference on Logistics Engineering, Management and Computer Science (LEMCS 2014)	Atlantis Press	The corresponding performance evaluation index system of the TACIT information resource system, the TACIT information management process, and the TACIT information management situation system are created, based on the structure of the entire enterprise TACIT information management system, and the information dimension of TACIT management

2.	Internal or External Knowledge: Which is More Important for the Performance of National Laboratories in Technology Latecomer Countries?	(Ploykiti koon & Weber, 2015)	Proceedings of PICMET '15: Management of the Technology Age	PICMET	Whatever the task, information from external sources affects performance more than internal information
3.	Firm performance in the periphery: on the relation between firm-internal knowledge and local knowledge spillovers	(Grillitsh & Nilsson, 2017)	Regional Studies, 2016	Taylor & Francis	Companies with weak internal knowledge grow faster in knowledge-intensive areas
4.	The impact of tacit knowledge management on organizational performance: Evidence from Malaysia	(Muthueloo et al., 2017)	Asia Pacific Management Review 22 (2017) 192-201	Elsevier Taiwan	The importance of knowledge creation and management, especially tacit knowledge, for both researchers and practitioners. This is especially important for senior leaders in any organization who want to achieve success and improve their organization's performance for better business performance and return on investment
5.	Influence of Strategic Knowledge Management on Firm Innovativeness and Performance	(Davila et al., 2019)	Brazilian Business Review		Brazilian companies focus on managing tacit knowledge and there are opportunities to improve performance if they focus more on tacit knowledge. Recommendations on choice practices and

					<p>tacit knowledge management are important inputs to support management decisions regarding resource allocation to improve innovation and efficiency</p>
6.	<p>The Importance of Internal Knowledge Generation and External Knowledge Sourcing for Sme Innovation and Performance: Evidence from Ireland</p>	<p>(Doran et al., 2019)</p>	<p>International Journal of Innovation Management</p>	<p>World Scientific Publishing Europe Ltd</p>	<p>Backward linkage has a positive effect on SME product innovation, but negatively on SME process innovation, while public information sources are positively related to the possibility of product innovation realization. This could have significant political implications</p>
7.	<p>Internal Factors Affect Knowledge Management and Firm Performance: A Systematic Review</p>	<p>(Mehrez et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Systems and Informatics 2020 pp 632-643</p>	<p>Springer</p>	<p>Information management is positively related to the results of the company. Many factors influence hubungan these, such as organizational learning, intellectual capital, human resource management, information technology, soft total quality management, knowledge management practices, strategies, structures</p>
8.	<p>How to encourage lecturer performance in research through servant leadership, organizational commitment,</p>	<p>(Winarno & Hermana, 2021)</p>	<p>Jurnal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa Vol. 14 No.1 Maret 202: 35-48</p>		<p>Focuses on the discreet exchange of research-related information, especially regarding research methodology and the development of practical methods. From a practical perspective, research requires the</p>

	and tacit knowledge sharing				expansion and development of a structured discreet exchange of information supported by cultural exchange between faculties
9.	Did the global financial crisis impact firms' innovation performance? The role of internal and external knowledge capabilities in high and lowtech industries	(Zouaghi et al., 2018)	Technological Forecasting & Social Change	Elsevier	The importance of human resources in activating internal capabilities as a coping mechanism in the low-tech sector during the economic crisis. Therefore, open innovation can help companies minimize resource constraints and innovation risks, especially during financial crises. The study provides valuable information for managers who want to develop strong internal knowledge in order to remain competitive in uncertain economic conditions
10.	Exploring the performance of tacit knowledge: How to make ordinary T people deliver extraordinary results in teams	(Olaisen & Revang, 2018)	International Journal of Information Management 43 (2018) 295–304	Elsevier	Rotation of professional roles in a team is successful if the team has enough time to develop social processes. When professionals are given direction, trust, accountability, and time to develop results, they step out of their comfort zone and together create exceptional results

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the description above, the literature obtained from the three variables in this paper was found and has been implemented and found, it's just that the lack of literature discussed, making this paper only photograph not optimal and the results of this paper represent the three existing variables. These three variables from the day of the resume in this paper support and accept the existing findings, just not yet satisfying. The existing phenomena and problems above have not all been answered from the literature found and implemented. To that end, the results in this paper represent and add color to the world of Human Resources.

The existing literature has provided an overview of the implementation of the three variables needed in this paper so that the results of this paper as conveyed in the results can be fulfilled and supported even though it is not satisfactory or maximal. The color of these findings could indicate a contribution, especially in the field of human resources and the use of this variable.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMENDATION

The implementation of these three variables already exists, it's just not related to all variables in one literature in one paper, this paper provides an answer that these variables already exist, and the problems presented above are answered even though they are not optimal and satisfactory in this paper.

FURTHER AND RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Implementation Tacit Knowledge, Internal Knowledge on Performance Management: (Systematic Literature Review)".

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